

PANOPTES: A Digital Twin Ontology for Cultural Asset Management

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Abstract—In this paper we present PANOPTES, a digital twin ontology designed to support dynamic monitoring, predictive analytics, and decision-making in the management of cultural heritage assets. Building on standards such as CIDOC CRM, SOSA/SSN, PROV-O, GeoSPARQL, and OWL-Time, PANOPTES introduces a unified semantic model that represents assets, observations, diagnoses, predictions, threats, and decision processes. The ontology naturally maps to a relational backend, enabling efficient data ingestion, traceability, and operational deployment. Application scenarios include condition monitoring, risk forecasting, emergency response, and preventive conservation planning. PANOPTES enables structured monitoring, predictive threat modeling, and decision support for the preventive conservation of cultural heritage assets, particularly in remote and infrastructure-poor sites.

Index Terms—cultural heritage, ontology, data modeling, digital twins, relational model, ARGUS project

I. INTRODUCTION

The preservation of cultural heritage (CH) assets increasingly depends on digital documentation, semantic modeling, and predictive monitoring. While established standards such as CIDOC CRM, Dublin Core, and LIDO provide structured descriptions of static metadata, they fall short in addressing emerging needs for continuous environmental monitoring, integration of sensor networks, and forecasting of deterioration risks. Existing ontologies typically model isolated aspects of heritage management and lack mechanisms to support dynamic, multimodal, and predictive representations across the full conservation pipeline. In this paper, we introduce PANOPTES, a comprehensive semantic and relational model designed to bridge this gap by unifying observation, diagnosis, prediction, and decision support for cultural heritage assets.

II. STATE OF THE ART: ONTOLOGIES FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE ASSETS

Ontologies play a pivotal role in the cultural heritage (CH) domain, providing structured frameworks to represent and manage complex information about cultural assets. They enable semantic interoperability, facilitating data sharing and integration across diverse institutions, research projects, and platforms. As CH practices evolve, there is increasing demand for ontologies capable of supporting dynamic, multimodal, and predictive management of heritage assets.

A. Foundational Cultural Heritage Ontologies

The *CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM)* [1] is the foundational ontology for cultural heritage

documentation. Standardized as ISO 21127:2014, it provides a formal structure to describe implicit and explicit relationships between heritage entities, aiming to achieve semantic interoperability between heterogeneous data sources. Complementary to CIDOC CRM, the *Lightweight Information Describing Objects (LIDO)* schema [2] enables the harvesting and sharing of museum and cultural heritage metadata, designed for interoperability with portals such as Europeana. The *Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI)* [3] offers a simpler, widely adopted set of metadata terms, although not specialized for cultural heritage, often serving as a foundation for interoperability at a basic descriptive level. While these models promote interoperability and documentation, they primarily focus on static descriptions and lack constructs for dynamic monitoring, real-time data integration, or predictive analysis.

B. Specialized and Extended Models

Extensions to CIDOC CRM address specific domain needs. *CRMdig* models the provenance of digital objects, *CRMsci* models scientific observation and measurement activities, and *CRMba* focuses on archaeological stratigraphy. The *Europeana Data Model (EDM)*[4] aggregates metadata from cultural heritage institutions across Europe, compatible with CIDOC CRM and Dublin Core, to emphasize flexible representation of complex digital cultural objects. The *Arches Project*[5] provides a geospatially-enabled, open-source platform for cultural heritage inventories, leveraging CIDOC CRM as its semantic core. These extensions and platforms enhance semantic expressivity and interoperability but continue to emphasize descriptive metadata rather than supporting dynamic monitoring, predictive maintenance, or decision-making processes.

C. Emerging Ontologies and Applications

Recent work has extended cultural heritage ontologies to accommodate dynamic representations and real-time data. Niccolucci et al. [6] introduced the *Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (HDTO)*, which builds on CIDOC CRM to model the evolving conditions of heritage assets. Follow-up studies explored methods for semantically populating such digital spaces [7] and promoted their use as interdisciplinary research infrastructures [8]. The *Reactive Heritage Digital Twin Ontology (RHDTO)* [9] further expands HDTO by incorporating sensors and actuators, enabling real-time interaction between digital twins and physical environments. In

contrast to HDTO and RHDTO—which emphasize condition documentation—PANOPTES models evolving conditions, predictive trajectories, and decision logic through formal entities like *Diagnosis*, *Prediction*, and *Decision*, supporting traceable, policy-informed risk mitigation. Felicetti and Niccolucci [10] advocate AI-enhanced ontological frameworks that integrate predictive analytics and risk assessment—objectives closely aligned with PANOPTES, which formalizes a unified schema for measurements, diagnoses, predictions, threats, and conservation decisions. In parallel, the *Cultural Gems Ontology* [11] models cultural and creative spaces across Europe, adhering to FAIR principles and enabling cross-domain semantic interoperability. Collectively, these developments reflect a shift toward dynamic, sensor-informed ontologies. Yet, comprehensive semantic modeling for predictive conservation and decision support remains limited—an area directly addressed by PANOPTES.

D. State-of-the-Art in Semantic Cultural Heritage Monitoring

Semantic web technologies are increasingly used in cultural heritage (CH) to enable interoperability, rich annotation, and intelligent analytics. The *CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM)* [1], an ISO standard, serves as a foundational ontology for describing artifacts, events, and actors. Extensions such as LIDO [2] and the Europeana Data Model (EDM) [4] support metadata harmonization across collections. However, these models emphasize static descriptions and lack support for dynamic sensor data or predictive analysis. Simpler schemas like Dublin Core [3] offer basic fields but are insufficient for modeling provenance or observations. As noted in [12], linked data enrich descriptions but require additional layers for real-time monitoring or decision support.

In parallel, the rise of IoT and sensor networks has led to new standards for observational data. The W3C/OGC SOSA/SSN stack [13] enables descriptions of sensors, actuators, and time-stamped observations. SOSA provides a lightweight core, while SSN adds semantics for measurement procedures and system structures, widely used across domains including smart cities and scientific monitoring.

In CH applications, SOSA/SSN has been used to annotate environmental data (e.g., temperature, humidity) and visitor interactions. The *exhiSTORY* framework [14] illustrates embedded IoT annotations in exhibits that communicate within a semantic environment. Similarly, Kotis et al. [15] developed *SmartMuseumOnto*, which combines SOSA/SSN with domain-specific modules for trustworthy IoT entities in museums. These examples demonstrate the relevance of semantic IoT ontologies for CH, while also underscoring the need for extensions to meet all requirements.

Provenance and trust are crucial for integrating heterogeneous CH and sensor data. The W3C PROV-O ontology [16] offers a general model for capturing data lineage (Entity, Activity, Agent), which can be specialized for CH (e.g., curator or sensor attribution). For spatiotemporal context, OGC’s GeoSPARQL [17] defines geometry classes and spatial relations in RDF, while W3C’s OWL-Time [18] supports event-

based temporal descriptions. These ontologies enable complex queries (e.g., “find all temperature readings within 1 km of this building in the last week”), but require alignment with CH ontologies for meaningful domain-specific integration.

Over the past decade, research has focused on combining these semantic technologies for CH IoT and analytics. Semantic IoT prototypes such as *exhiSTORY* [14] and *SmartMuseumOnto* [15] integrate SOSA/SSN with CIDOC CRM, GeoSPARQL, and OWL-Time to relate sensor data to museum objects and spaces. Bibliometric studies confirm growing interest in “semantic cultural heritage” to achieve interoperability and advanced applications (e.g., 3D visualization, multisensory experiences), often citing CIDOC CRM and linked data as foundations. On the predictive modeling front, ontologies like the *Manufacturing Predictive Maintenance Ontology (MPMO)* [19] illustrate how event chronicles and numerical constraints can be represented in OWL for maintenance tasks. While MPMO targets industrial machinery, it demonstrates the potential of semantic models to support prediction by formalizing conditions and expected outcomes. However, to date, no ontology has been published that models the prediction of deterioration or risks for cultural assets in a similar manner, highlighting a significant gap.

E. Limitations and Motivation for PANOPTES

No single ontology currently addresses all needs for CH asset monitoring. Sensor ontologies like SOSA/SSN model devices and observations but do not include CH-specific domain classes such as *Artifact* or *ConservationEvent*. Heritage ontologies like CIDOC CRM richly capture artifacts and historical events but lack native constructs for real-time measurements or IoT processes. Spatial and temporal ontologies such as GeoSPARQL and OWL-Time provide location and timing classes and relations but remain orthogonal to domain semantics. Provenance models like PROV-O ensure data traceability but must be customized for CH applications. Moreover, predictive analytics concepts (e.g., anomaly detection, risk forecasting, maintenance prediction) are not natively defined in existing standards. Although MPMO offers an example in manufacturing, CH monitoring requires specific abstractions, such as condition scores for a fresco over time. In practice, deployments have often had to integrate multiple ontologies with ad-hoc mappings. For instance, in *SmartMuseumOnto* [15], MESO is reused alongside SOSA/SSN, CIDOC CRM, and GeoNames to capture all facets; however, the authors acknowledge that “existing ontologies do not fully cover the Smart Museum objectives,” leading to the need for additional custom classes. Existing ontologies each advance the field within specific niches, but their integration has required extensive engineering. Despite substantial development, several challenges persist:

- **Complexity and Usability:** Ontologies like CIDOC CRM are intricate, hindering adoption by institutions lacking specialized expertise.
- **Dynamic and Multimodal Data Representation:** Traditional models often struggle to represent temporal evo-

lution, real-time condition monitoring, and multimodal environmental data.

- **Interoperability:** Mapping between heterogeneous data models and ontologies remains a major effort, requiring more standardized and modular integration approaches.

Semantic link discovery works have combined GeoSPARQL relations with SOSA/SSN triples to align visitor trajectories in museums. Yet most prior efforts have focused either on descriptive data modeling (e.g., CIDOC CRM) or enabling rule-based reasoning (e.g., MPMO with SWRL), without addressing the full pipeline from raw sensor data to decision support for CH conservation.

These gaps motivate the development of new ontological frameworks that balance semantic richness with practical applicability, supporting dynamic, multimodal, and spatiotemporal dimensions of cultural heritage management. The *ARGUS PANOPTES* ontology is proposed to address the current limitations in existing cultural heritage ontologies. By formally aligning SOSA/SSN with CIDOC CRM and PROV-O (and integrating OWL-Time and GeoSPARQL), it avoids ad-hoc semantic solutions. Moreover, PANOPTES introduces semantic constructs for predictive analytics, conservation-specific provenance, and decision support, offering a coherent framework for risk mitigation and informed preservation planning.

III. THE PANOPTES ONTOLOGY AND MODEL

A. Motivation

The PANOPTES ontology was developed to address the challenges of documenting, monitoring, analyzing, and predicting the condition and evolution of cultural heritage (CH) assets. Traditional heritage ontologies primarily focus on static descriptions. In contrast, PANOPTES introduces an integrated, dynamic, and predictive model capable of representing measurements, observations, risks, and decision-making processes within a unified framework.

B. Design Principles

The design of PANOPTES is driven by the following core principles:

- **Asset-Centric Representation:** Every measurement, observation, and computational model is ultimately related back to a specific cultural asset.
- **Dynamic State Monitoring:** The ontology supports capturing measurements and diagnosing condition changes of assets over time.
- **Predictive Modeling:** PANOPTES integrates computational models, diagnostic activities, predictions, and decision-making mechanisms.
- **Semantic Interoperability:** The ontology aligns with established standards (SOSA/SSN, PROV-O, GeoSPARQL, OWL-Time, CIDOC CRM) to ensure maximum interoperability.
- **Relational Implementation Readiness:** The structure of classes and relationships is designed to facilitate straightforward implementation within relational databases.

C. Core Concepts and Classes

The PANOPTES ontology defines a set of core entities:

- **Asset:** A cultural heritage entity, modeled as a specialization of a Feature of Interest (`sosa:FeatureOfInterest`) and a geospatial Feature (`geo:Feature`).
- **Measurement:** A specialization of Observation (`sosa:Observation`), representing observational data collected about the Asset.
- **Instrument:** A specialization of Sensor (`sosa:Sensor`), describing the device or method used to perform a Measurement.
- **Quantity:** A quantified result associated with a Measurement.
- **Diagnosis:** A specialized Activity (`prov:Activity`) interpreting Measurement data to assess the Asset's condition.
- **Prediction:** A specialized Entity (`prov:Entity`) representing forecasts derived from Diagnoses and Computational Models.
- **Computational Model:** A method or algorithm (`dul:Method`) used for diagnosing or predicting asset conditions.
- **Visualization:** A visual output associated with a Computational Model's results.
- **Protocol:** Defines procedures followed during Measurements and is linked to Instruments.
- **Policy and Rule:** Structures that regulate decision-making processes concerning asset conservation or intervention.
- **Decision:** A process resulting from Diagnosis and Prediction, determining conservation actions based on defined Policies and Rules.
- **Threat:** A risk or damaging factor potentially affecting an Asset.
- **Cultural Documentation:** A specialized Document (`cidoc-crm:E31_Document`) related to observations or activities concerning an Asset.
- **Event:** A specialization of Event (`cidoc-crm:E5_Event`), representing incidents or processes impacting the Asset.

A structured overview of these classes and their key relationships is presented in TABLE I.

D. Relations Between Classes

PANOPTES defines the following relationships:

- An **Asset** is documented by **Cultural Documentation** and measured through **Measurements**.
- A **Measurement** uses an **Instrument**, follows a **Protocol**, and quantifies a **Quantity**.
- A **Measurement** captures spatial (`geo:Geometry`) and temporal (`time:Instant`) attributes.
- A **Diagnosis** interprets Measurements and is generated by a **Computational Model**.
- A **Prediction** is derived from Computational Models and Diagnoses.

TABLE I
CORE CLASSES AND RELATIONS IN THE PANOPTES ONTOLOGY

Class	Description and Key Relations
Asset	Cultural heritage entity; measured by Measurements; documented by Cultural Documentation.
Measurement	Observation of Asset; uses Instrument; quantifies Quantity; follows Protocol; records time and location.
Instrument	Device or sensor used in a Measurement.
Quantity	Quantified result produced by a Measurement.
Diagnosis	Interpretation of Measurements; generated by a Computational Model.
Prediction	Forecast based on Diagnosis and Computational Models.
Computational Model	Algorithm/method generating Diagnoses and Predictions; results visualized by Visualizations.
Visualization	Visual representation of Computational Model outputs.
Protocol	Procedure for performing Measurements; linked to Instruments.
Decision	Informed by Diagnosis and Prediction; guided by Policies and governed by Rules.
Policy	Regulatory framework guiding Decisions.
Rule	Specific guideline derived from a Policy; regulates Threats.
Threat	Risk factor affecting the Asset; associated with Events.
Event	Incident or process impacting the Asset.
Cultural Documentation	Document describing the Asset or related activities and events.

- A **Decision** is informed by Diagnoses and Predictions, follows a **Policy**, and specifies a **Rule**.
- A **Rule** regulates a **Threat** affecting the Asset.
- An **Event** may be linked to Threats and can be triggered by Computational Models or external causes.
- A **Visualization** depicts the output of a Computational Model.

E. Ontological Alignment and Reuse

PANOPTES is designed to maximize semantic interoperability through alignment with internationally recognized ontologies:

- **SOSA/SSN** [20]: Provides the foundation for modeling observations and instruments. Measurements are subclasses of `sosa:Observation`, Instruments are subclasses of `sosa:Sensor`.
- **PROV-O** [21]: Models provenance information. Diagnoses are instances of `prov:Activity`, Predictions are `prov:Entity`.
- **GeoSPARQL** [17]: Supports geospatial aspects, with Assets defined as `geo:Feature` linked to `geo:Geometry`.
- **OWL-Time** [22]: Provides primitives for modeling temporal aspects of Measurements and Events.
- **CIDOC CRM** [23]: Facilitates cultural documentation and event modeling via alignment with `E31_Document` and `E5_Event`.
- **DUL (Descriptive Ontology for Linguistic and Cognitive Engineering)** [24]: Provides concepts for modeling Computational Models, Decisions, and Policies.

The core alignment between PANOPTES classes and external ontologies is summarized in TABLE II.

F. Relational Model Mapping

The ontology maps naturally into a relational schema. Each core class corresponds to a relational table, and object properties are modeled as foreign key relationships. Analytical workflows—such as the chain from Diagnosis to Prediction to

TABLE II
PANOPTES CORE CLASSES AND THEIR ONTOLOGICAL ALIGNMENTS

PANOPTES Class	Mapped Ontology Concept
Asset	<code>sosa:FeatureOfInterest</code> , <code>geo:Feature</code>
Measurement	<code>sosa:Observation</code>
Instrument	<code>sosa:Sensor</code>
Quantity	(new concept, linked internally to Measurement)
Diagnosis	<code>prov:Activity</code>
Prediction	<code>prov:Entity</code>
Computational Model	<code>dul:Method</code>
Visualization	(custom class)
Protocol	(custom class)
Policy	<code>dul:Policy</code>
Decision	<code>dul:Decision</code>
Threat	(custom class)
Event	<code>cidoc-crm:E5_Event</code>
Cultural Documentation	<code>cidoc-crm:E31_Document</code>

Decision—are traceable across linked tables, enabling efficient queries and complex reasoning over asset conditions and risks.

A schematic overview of the relational structure is depicted in Fig. 1.

IV. APPLICATION SCENARIOS

PANOPTES has been designed to support a wide range of applications in monitoring, management, and conservation planning of cultural heritage assets. Its multimodal and dynamic structure allows integration of diverse data sources, tracking of spatiotemporal changes, and support for decision-making processes. Key scenarios include:

- **Condition Monitoring and Diagnostic Assessment:** Continuous and periodic measurements (e.g., structural displacement, surface humidity) collected via sensors are analyzed by Computational Models to detect early deterioration signs. Diagnoses document evolving conditions and support proactive conservation strategies.
- **Risk Prediction and Preventive Conservation:** Time-series environmental data (e.g., temperature, seismic activity) feed Predictions of future risks. Computational Models forecast threats such as structural failure, guiding

Fig. 1. Relational model derived from the PANOPTES ontology.

preventive maintenance decisions through Policy-driven frameworks.

- **Emergency Response and Post-Event Analysis:** Following events (e.g., earthquakes, floods), new Measurements and Diagnoses rapidly assess damage severity. Predictions inform emergency stabilization, and Cultural Documentation enriches asset records for insurance and restoration needs.
- **Multimodal Heritage Digitization:** PANOPTES integrates 3D scans, multispectral imagery, sensor data, and historical documentation, enabling rich digital twins for research and public engagement.
- **Decision Support Systems for Conservation Management:** Heritage authorities prioritize interventions based on real-time Monitoring, predicted degradation, and regulatory frameworks encoded as Policies and Rules. While PANOPTES is ontology-driven and not prescriptive in logic, it supports both expert-driven and rule-based decision-making. This flexibility is essential in remote contexts, where real-time human oversight may be limited and recommendations must often be derived from sensor thresholds, predictive models, or historical patterns. Visualization modules assist stakeholders in understanding risks and impacts.

A representative example illustrating the design intentions of PANOPTES is the cellar town of Baltanás in Spain—one of the largest underground wine cellar complexes in Europe, comprising 374 interconnected cellars carved into stratified clay and arranged over six superimposed levels. While the site is near the town of Baltanás and is partially maintained by the local community, its overall preservation remains challenging due to the vast scale of the complex. Only selected cellars are monitored or conserved at a time, while others face persistent issues such as high humidity, insufficient ventilation, and structural vulnerability.

In this context, PANOPTES is designed to model cellar structures as *Assets*, with environmental conditions captured through sensor-derived *Measurements* (e.g., humidity, airflow, and displacement), temporally and spatially annotated. Potential risks such as moisture-induced deterioration or soil movement can be semantically formalized through *Diagnosis* and *Prediction* entities, feeding into conservation *Decisions* aligned with predefined *Policies* and *Rules*. For instance, the ontology can express that a pro-

longed period of high humidity and low airflow—diagnosed from time-series data—triggers a preventive recommendation for passive ventilation reinforcement. While PANOPTES has not yet been deployed at Baltanás, this scenario reflects its envisioned utility in supporting scalable, risk-informed conservation management within the ARGUS framework.

V. FORESEEN IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

The practical deployment of PANOPTES follows a layered architecture bridging semantic modeling and operational systems.

The PANOPTES ontology will be implemented through a relational backend, where each core class is mapped to a corresponding relational table, and object properties are implemented via foreign key constraints to ensure referential integrity and efficient queries. Foreign keys will represent object properties (relations), ensuring referential integrity and supporting efficient queries. The relational model directly mirrors the ontology structure, facilitating dynamic updates and multimodal integration. To implement the PANOPTES ontology in a scalable and operationally effective manner, a relational database backend has been designed. The structure maps each core PANOPTES class to a dedicated relational table, while object properties are implemented via foreign key constraints ensuring data integrity and traceability. The Entity Mapping is as follows:

- **Asset:** `monument` table (location, construction period, materials).
- **Measurement:** `measurement` table, linking `Assets`, `Quantities`, `Protocols`.
- **Instrument** and **Protocol:** separate tables supporting measurement workflows.
- **Diagnosis, Prediction, Decision:** tables reflecting diagnostic and risk management processes.
- **Cultural Documentation:** `cultural_documentation` table.
- **Threats, Rules, Policies, and Events:** interconnected tables supporting monitoring, risk assessment, and emergency workflows.

Sensor measurements, diagnostic activities, and observational data will be continuously ingested into the database. Measurements will be recorded along with their provenance, time, location, associated protocols, and instruments. Real-time updates will enable the tracking of the evolving state of

assets, supporting condition monitoring and documentation. Diagnosis activities and Computational Models will analyze the collected measurements to generate Predictions regarding asset deterioration or risks. Decision entities will be instantiated based on Diagnoses and Predictions, aligned with encoded Policies and Rules, thus supporting evidence-based preventive conservation strategies. The architecture foresees the development of digital twins for cultural assets, where the asset's real-world state is mirrored and updated dynamically in a digital environment. Measurements, Diagnoses, Predictions, and Decision-making processes modeled in PANOPTES will drive the evolution of the digital twin, supporting simulations, scenario testing, and immersive visualization. PANOPTES-based implementations will leverage open standards such as SOSA/SSN, PROV-O, GeoSPARQL, and OWL-Time for interoperability with external systems and datasets. By adhering to FAIR data principles, the system will facilitate data sharing, reuse, and integration with broader cultural heritage and smart city infrastructures.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

PANOPTES provides a scalable and extensible framework for cultural heritage management, combining ontological expressiveness with relational database efficiency. Through asset-centric modeling, spatiotemporal traceability, and multimodal sensor integration, it addresses key limitations of existing models. Its modular design supports evolving conservation practices, while integration with standards like SOSA/SSN, PROV-O, and CIDOC CRM ensures interoperability and enables comprehensive digital twin construction. Crucially, PANOPTES supports AI-driven predictive maintenance to anticipate deterioration.

Despite its operational focus, real-world deployment poses challenges, including heterogeneous sensor data integration, high-frequency measurement scalability, legacy system compatibility, and uncertain observation handling. Addressing these will be essential for robust predictive workflows and digital twin reliability. Future work will also explore ontology evolution to support new asset types and sensing technologies.

Upcoming deployments within the ARGUS project will validate PANOPTES across multiple heritage sites. We will also refine backend infrastructure, improve interfaces, and incorporate advanced visualization, enhancing stakeholder interaction.

Long-term, PANOPTES aims to evolve into a smart heritage management platform, fostering immersive engagement for researchers, conservators, and the public.

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